

Development of High Performance Discontinuous Fibres – Fibre Surface Modification

T. R. Pozegic*, M. L. Longana, S. Huntley, S. He, R. M. I. Bandara¹, S.G. King¹ and I. Hamerton.
Bristol Composite Institute (ACCIS), Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, Bristol, U. K.
¹Advanced Technology Institute, University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey, U.K
*t.pozegic@bristol.ac.uk

The HiPerDiF technology, invented and patented by University of Bristol, is a high speed process to produce highly aligned discontinuous fibre reinforced composites (ADFRCs).

I. HiPerDiF machine overview

Increasing Fibre-Throughput

A method to increase throughput from HiPerDiF is to increase quantity of feedstock, furthermore, to increase stability of short fibres in the aqueous solution

Zeta Potential

This refers to the charge formation when the fibre is submerged in an aqueous solution. The greater the magnitude, the greater the stability. The results on the left are of a sized-removed, high modulus pitch-based carbon fibre (benchmark)

Surfactant	Surfactant Type
Brij 58	Non-ionic
Pluronic F127	Non-ionic
SDS	Anionic
SDBS	Anionic
Triton X-100	Non-ionic
Triton X-405	Non-ionic
Tween 80	Non-ionic

Surfactants

Non-covalent functionalisation does not reduce the tensile performance of the fibres. A range of surfactants were trialled (left table), with SDS determined the most appropriate at 1000 critical micelle concentration (right). The improved fibre stability in aqueous solution is evident

Benchmark

1000 CMC

Viscosity

Increasing the viscosity is an effective way to stabilise micro-sized fibres in solution. This is potentially the main mechanism for the 1000 CMC having superior dispersion

Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS)

Single fibre fragmentation tests revealed no statistically significant differences between the benchmark (BM) and SDSB-modified fibres

Future Work

Through this programme, the quantity of feedstock has increased by ~2 orders of magnitude. However, additional work is needed to determine how increases in solution viscosity affect the production through the HiPerDiF machine.

VI. Industrial partners